

APPLICATION OF QUEST TECHNOLOGY IN COLLOID CHEMISTRY LESSONS

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Abstract. This article contains information about modern pedagogical technologies, the effective use of modern pedagogical technologies in colloid chemistry classes and their importance.

Keywords: "pedagogical technology", "technology", "educational technology", "Quest", "Dispers", "Colloid", "Lyophob", "Lyophile", Phenolphthalein.

INTRODUCTION

Today, there is a need to create the necessary methodical conditions for improving students' knowledge and the mechanism of developing their professional competence in designing lessons, and it is appropriate to use interactive education, especially "Quest" technology, in developing their competence in designing lessons.

Below I will give an example of the development of a lesson in colloid chemistry designed on the basis of "Quest technology" (Table 1).

Table 1.

An example of lesson development designed on the basis of Quest technology

Composition of elements	Quest development requirements and content
Quest type	About the ring quest.
Quest direction	On the topic "Dispersed systems and their classification". Quests can be used in Colloidal Chemistry classes and extracurricular activities.
Goals and objectives	Purpose: generalization and systematization of knowledge on the topic "Dispersed systems and their classification"; Demonstration of preparation of liquid and solid dispersed phase systems and emulsions on the topic "Dispersed systems and their classification" with the help of experiment. Duties: 1. Improving students' skills on the topic "Dispersed systems and their classification", the following: - analyze and find non-standard ways to solve problems; - modeling of real situations, study of built models, interpretation of obtained results; - to recognize drawings, models and substances used in life; 2. Encouragement to connect students to the results aimed at forming their skills: - to see a mathematical problem in the context of a problematic situation in everyday life;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - finding information in various sources for solving problems; - decision-making in conditions of incomplete and redundant, accurate and probable information; - planning and implementation of activities aimed at solving problematic tasks. <p>3. Helping students to achieve personal results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the ability to clearly and reasonably express one's thoughts, to prove with examples and vice versa; - thoughts about chemistry as a field of human activity, its importance for its renewal and development; - creativity of thinking, initiative, resourcefulness, activity in solving problems.
Term	Short term. 2 hours (1 pair)
Age of participants / target group	Students are 12 listeners
Quest scenario	The training room will be equipped with various didactic materials and information communication technologies
Quest heroes	Teams: "Dispers", "Colloid", "Lyofob", "Lyofil".
Quest plan and supporting path	<p>The research results are achieved by performing the tasks presented as various didactic materials by teams in a predetermined direction. The same amount of time is allocated for each stage, after the task is completed, the teams move from one stage to the next. The winner is the team that passed all the stages and collected all the words.</p> <p>Quest Stages:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) "Dispersed systems and their classification"; 2) "Classification of dispersed systems according to the aggregate state of dispersed phase and dispersed medium"; 3) "Break"; 4) "Formula for calculating the spherical surface of dispersed phase particles".
Tasks, obstacles	If the team fails to complete the task, makes a mistake, it is necessary to perform an additional task.
Directions	To pass the stages, you need to quickly locate the next stage along a predetermined route and try not to miss any of them.
Sources	<p>To prepare for the quest, participating students are invited to repeat the material on the following topic:</p> <p>Experiments on the topic "Dispersed systems and their classification".</p>

Electronic learning resources	Multimedia applications, educational resources with presentations, video assignments (social), electronic gadgets.
Technical device and equipment	Video mirror, modern computer technologies, mobile devices.
Criteria for evaluating student performance	For a correctly completed task, they get letters given in English (corresponding to the name of the group).
The result of the quest is a learning "product" and reflection	The result of the quest is related to the performance of the main task: the participants show the words they have found and discuss their translation.

Teams are routed through the following quest stages (Table 2).

Table 2.

Quest Stages

Name of teams	Quest Stages			
	Dispersed systems and their classification	Classification of dispersed systems according to the aggregate state of the dispersed phase and dispersed medium	A break	The formula for calculating the spherical surface of dispersed phase particles
"Dispers"	1	2	3	4
"Colloid"	2	3	4	1
"lyophobe"	3	4	1	2
"Lyophile"	4	1	2	3

1st stage.

"Dispersed systems and their classification".

Materials and equipment: Textbook, visual aids.

2nd stage.

"Disperse systems are classified according to the state of the dispersed phase and the dispersed medium aggregate".

Materials and equipment: cards, pen, answer sheet.

At this stage, the participating students should write on their respective cardboard papers that the dispersed systems are classified according to the state of the dispersed phase and the dispersed medium aggregate (Table 3).

No	Disperse environment	Disperse phase	Conditional sign	Examples
1	gas	gas		
2	gas	liquid		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
3	gas	hard		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
4	liquid	gas		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
5	liquid	liquid		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
6	liquid	hard		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
7	hard	gas		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
8	hard	liquid		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
9	hard	hard		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>

Figure 1. Questions.

Answers:

Foam; fog; cloud

Smoke; dust powder

Many peaks; gas emulsion; spray

Emulsion; milk; in the water oil; in oil water; in gasoline water; Mayonnaise.

Suspension; waste water; tooth paste

Hard many peaks; hard aerosol; bread; pumice stone; coal; foam plastic.

Pearl; gel; cement;

Alloy; colored glass; hard suspension.

3rd stage.

"Break".

are offered to relax and solve a crossword based on the topic .

Materials and equipment: crossword handout, pencil.

KROSSVORD

WIDTH

2. What is a laboratory device designed to transfer a certain volume of liquid from one container to another container? [PIPETTE]

4. Which indicator is used to determine the working alkali solution?
[PHENOPHTHALEIN]

6. Electron reactions in the same atom or other than ions to the circumstances as it passes happened to be type of reaction determine g . [OXIDATION-REDUCTION]

7. What is the name of the 25 ml, 50 ml laboratory equipment designed to measure the volume of flowing liquid? [BURETTE]

10. Oxidation – What is the second name of the return method? [OXIDOMETRY]
ALL OVER

1. "It is possible to study the and quantitative composition of various substances and their mixtures". Points in place define the word [QUALITY]

3. What is the name of this ion K^+ ? [POTASSIUM]

Which method is most often used in grav and metric analysis? [DROWN]

8. How many classes are dispersion systems divided? [THREE]

9. What color does it turn to when it reaches the equivalence point when titrating a working alkali solution? [PINK]

4th stage. "Finding Arithmetic Formulas in Sequences" (Fig. 2) .

Materials and equipment: notebook, pen.

$$S = 4 \cdot \pi \cdot R^2$$

$$S = \pi \cdot R^2$$

$$S = \frac{4 \cdot \pi \cdot R^3}{3}$$

Figure 2. Flower garden.

CONCLUSION

It is effective to use the above-mentioned technological map and model lesson developments in the development of competence related to the design of lessons in the system of continuous professional development using "Quest" technology .

This presented technological map and model lesson developments continuously improve the content, stages, algorithm and methods of introducing students to science innovations and various teaching technologies in the educational process.

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